

1 **PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND *IN VITRO* CATION RELEASE RELEVANCE OF**
2 **THERAPEUTIC MUDS “MADURATION”**

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19 **Abstract**

20 Therapeutic muds are used in the treatment of illnesses of the locomotor apparatus,
21 including osteoarthritis and rheumatologic diseases. The mechanisms of action of this
22 therapy are a matter of discussion, mainly for the different traditions of pelotherapy
23 centers. Heat plays a fundamental role in the beneficial effects of thermal mud therapy
24 together with the possible transfer across the skin barrier of chemical elements
25 presented in the mud. Preparation procedures of therapeutic muds have been orally
26 transmitted since ancient times, being accepted that muds require a “maturation”
27 process to achieve the desired therapeutic results. Pharmaceutical research of maturation
28 is crucial to ascertain the possible changes induced by this operation in the properties of
29 muds. In particular, it is necessary to verify the changes associated with physical and/or
30 chemical therapeutic mechanisms that sustain the traditional use of maturation in the
31 preparation of therapeutic muds. Two clay samples were used to prepare thermal muds
32 with mineral medicinal water from the thermal spring of Graena (Cortes y Graena,
33 Granada, Spain). Muds were matured for three months and characterized over time for
34 those properties considered relevant in view of their topical administration (rheological
35 properties and particle size distribution) and possible mechanisms of action
36 (composition, pH, cation exchange capacity, thermal properties and amount of cations
37 released). Maturation of the studied therapeutic muds did not induce alteration of clay
38 minerals, even if a decrease in amplitude of particle size distribution, changes in pH and
39 disappearance of thixotropic behavior were observed. Maturation increased the release
40 of cations from therapeutic muds but did not improve their thermal properties. In the
41 studied case, thermophysical activity did not require maturation. Conversely, maturation
42 increased the amount of cations released from the muds, appearing as a beneficial
43 process for possible chemical therapeutic effects associated with the ionic content of
44 these systems. Maturation could therefore explain the differential chemical effects
45 associated with the use of therapeutic muds compared to other thermotherapeutic
46 agents.

47 *Keywords:* Therapeutic muds; Maturation; Clays; Cation release; Specific heat.

48

49 **1. Introduction**

50 Clays are used in several European thermal centres to prepare semisolid suspensions
51 with mineral medicinal water (therapeutic muds) that are topically administered to treat
52 osteoarthritis and other musculoskeletal disorders (Grassi et al., 2003; Veniale et al.,
53 2007; Gomes et al., 2007, 2013; Bellometti et al., 2007; Evcik et al., 2007; Giacomino
54 and De Michele, 2007; Fraioli et al., 2011; Beer et al., 2013; Espejo-Antúnez et al.,
55 2013). These semisolid remedies, in which the clay behaves as vehicle of the mineral
56 medicinal water, are inorganic structured gels formed by the interactions between clay
57 particles suspended in mineral medicinal water (Viseras et al., 2007). The properties of
58 these systems greatly depend on the solid-liquid interfacial phenomena occurring during
59 “maturation” (Aguzzi et al., 2013). Maturation is an ethnopharmaceutical procedure that
60 involves the contact between clay particles and thermal waters for a certain period of
61 time (generally months), following local traditional protocols that greatly vary
62 depending on the thermal centres (Veniale et al., 2004; Baschini et al., 2010; Pozo et al.,
63 2013). It is assumed that virgin muds require maturation to optimise their therapeutic
64 effects, achieving the category of “matured muds” or “therapeutic muds” ready to be
65 used in pelotherapy (Gomes et al., 2013). Veniale et al. (2004) compared the
66 mineralogical composition and properties of virgin and matured clays from different
67 thermal centres of northern Italy concluding that the observed changes were mainly due
68 to the composition of the water. Smectite/water muds are considered optimal due to the
69 ability of smectitic clays to retain high amounts of water. This is consistent with the
70 correlation observed between thermal properties of muds and their relative amount of
71 water (Caridad et al., 2014). Cara et al. (2000a) found that therapeutic muds could be
72 improved by addition of smectite. Maturation of illitic-smectitic clays in bicarbonate
73 and sulphate rich waters induced reduction in the crystallinity of clay minerals,
74 dissolution of carbonates, precipitation of gypsum and changes in granulometry and
75 conductivity (Sánchez et al., 2002). Changes in crystallinity and granulometry were also
76 found in saponite and montmorillonite matured in seawater (Carretero et al., 2007),
77 kaolinite-saponite in sodium potassium chloride water (Gamiz et al., 2009) and kaolinite
78 and bentonite in bicarbonate rich waters (Fernández-González et al., 2013). Tateo et al.
79 (2010) described in detail the mineralogical changes occurring during short term (up to
80 2 months) and long term (up to 15 months) maturation of different clays in sulphate
81 mineral water, concluding the need for the study of each particular water-clay pair on
82 case-by-case basis. Pozo et al. (2013) compared matured muds from different Spanish

83 thermal stations and found pronounced differences in composition and properties, even
84 if the muds were used for similar clinical purposes.

85 The nature and importance of the mineralogical, textural and chemical changes induced
86 by the maturation process and mentioned above does not seem likely to have a decisive
87 influence on the therapeutic properties of therapeutic muds. In other words, the
88 mineralogical, textural and chemical differences observed by these authors hardly could
89 explain alone the clinical need to perform maturation of the mud. Recently, the
90 importance of elemental characterization of peloids has been evidenced and the
91 necessity of determining the bioavailability of soluble mineral species when the peloids
92 are applied has been suggested (Suárez Muñoz et al., 2015).

93 Maturation must be studied from a pharmaceutical point of view to understand its
94 importance in achieving therapeutic muds. The pharmaceutical development of a
95 matured therapeutic mud should be focused on achieving products suitable to the
96 purpose for which they are intended (Cerezo et al., 2014). In particular, as health care
97 products, therapeutic muds must be developed fulfilling technological,
98 biopharmaceutical and clinical features in order to ensure their stability, effectiveness
99 and safety.

100 With these premises, aim of this work was to evaluate the influence of maturation on
101 therapeutic muds prepared with two clay samples, commonly used in spa centers of
102 southern European/Mediterranean countries.

103

104 **2. Materials and methods**

105

106 **2.1. Materials**

107 Two clay samples (I, II) were used to prepare the thermal muds. Sample I was
108 Therapeutic mud Minerale[®] from SO.MI.ES. (Italy) and sample II came from Jebel
109 Aidoudi deposits (Tunisia). Both samples were fully characterized in a previous work in
110 terms of identity, richness and purity (Sánchez-Espejo et al., 2014). The samples were
111 identified as “high purity clays”, as the sum of smectites, kaolinite and illite was N 70%
112 w/w, with 13% w/w of calcite in sample I and 11% w/w of gypsum in sample II as main
113 mineral impurities. Both samples are used in several spas in Italy and Tunisia.

114

115 Mineral medicinal water used for the preparation of therapeutic muds came from
116 thermal spring of Graena (Cortes y Graena, Granada, Spain). Its physicochemical
117 characteristics were determined in a previous work (Aguzzi et al., 2013).

118

119 **2.2. Preparation of therapeutic muds**

120 1:2 (w/w) clay/water muds were prepared by using a turbine stirrer (Silverson LT, U.K.)
121 (4000 rpm, 5 min) and allowed to swell for 48 hours (samples I₀ and II₀). The resultant
122 systems were then stored at room temperature in airtight polyethylene containers for
123 three months. At the end of each month, the muds were manually stirred for 15 min by
124 means of a glass rod performing planetary movements and aliquots were taken to be
125 characterized (samples I₁, I₂, I₃, II₁, II₂ and II₃).

126

127 **2.3. Characterization of therapeutic muds**

128 Chemical and physical integrity of muds during maturation must be controlled by
129 measuring different parameters, including pH, cation exchange capacity, viscosity and
130 when necessary mineralogical and chemical compositions (Cerezo et al., 2014).

131

132 **2.3.1. Mineralogical and chemical composition**

133 X-Ray diffraction (XRD) data and chemical analysis (major elements) were done
134 following López-Galindo et al. (1996). XRD analysis were done by using a Philips® X-
135 Pert (Philips, Holanda) diffractometer equipped with automatic slit (CuK α , 4-70° 2 θ ,
136 6°/min, 40kV). Random powder diffraction was used on silt-clay fraction (the muds
137 were dispersed in water and the silt-clay fraction separated and then dried), and air-
138 dried/ethylene glycol solvated oriented- aggregates of the clay fractions were prepared
139 on glass slides. All oriented clay fractions were submitted to thermal treatments (550°C,
140 2 h). Data were analyzed with the Xpovder® software package (Martín-Ramos, 2004).
141 Major elements were determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF), using a Bruker® S4
142 Pioneer equipment, with a Rh X-ray tube (60 kV, 150 mA).

143

144 **2.3.2. Water content, pH and particle size distribution**

145 The water content of therapeutic muds was determined by weight loss on drying of 1 g
146 of mud. pH of the muds was measured by using a pHmeter (Crison, pH 25+) equipped
147 with a semisolid sensor (5052T).

148 Particle size changes of the solid phases, as a result of maturation, were measured with a

149 Malvern® Mastersizer 2000 LF granulometer. The muds were dispersed in water under
150 sonication. Data were online collected and statistical particle diameters (d_{10} , d_{50} , d_{90})
151 were calculated. SPAN factor was also calculated following Gavini et al. (2008) as an
152 index of the amplitude of particle size distribution. Three replicates were performed for
153 each sample.

154

155 **2.3.3. Cation exchange capacity (CEC)**

156 Dried mud powders (1 g) were dispersed in 25 mL tetramethylammonium bromide
157 aqueous solution (1 M), in order to displace their constituent cations. Dispersions were
158 shaken overnight at 50 rpm and then filtered. Cations in solution were assayed by ICP-
159 OES (Optima 8300 ICP-OES Spectrometeer, Perkin Elmer, USA) and CEC was
160 calculated as the sum of exchangeable cations, expressed in meq/100 g of dried mud.

161

162 **2.3.4. Rheological properties**

163 Rheological analysis was carried out with a Controlled Rate Viscometer (Thermo
164 Scientific HAAKE, RotoVisco 1) connected to a “personal computer” to set analysis
165 parameters, process and record data by means of HAAKE RheoWin software. A
166 plate/plate combination (Plate Ø 20 mm serrated PP20/S sensor system) was used as
167 measuring system. Measurements were carried out at 25°C after a rest time of 90 s. A
168 Peltier temperature controlled measuring plate for parallel plate (TCP/P, HAAKE unit)
169 was used to control measurement temperature. Rheological properties of the samples
170 were measured in the shear rate range 10-800 s^{-1} . Shear rates were selected as
171 representative of the stress produced by common operations like skin spreading (10–200
172 s^{-1}), manual mixing (100–200 s^{-1}) or container removal (400–2000 s^{-1}) (Schott, 1995).
173 Rheological characterization included thixotropic behavior, yield points and apparent
174 viscosities of the samples. Six replicates were performed on each sample.

175

176 **2.3.5. Thermal studies**

177 Cooling kinetics were studied following Cara et al. (2000b). Briefly, known amounts of
178 muds were conditioned at 50°C in a cylindrical polyethylene terephthalate cell and then
179 immersed in a thermostatic bath at 25°C, measuring the cooling of the samples up to
180 32°C, by means of a thermometric probe located in the center of the cell. Experimental
181 cooling data were fitted by using the Newton law, describing thermal exchange between
182 two bodies in contact at different temperatures.

183

184

$$(T - T_{min}) = (T_{max} - T_{min})e^{-kt} \quad (1)$$

185

186 where T_{min} was the room temperature (25°C), T_{max} was the initial temperature (50°C), t
187 was the time in minutes and k was a constant that depend on the material and apparatus,
188 given by:

189

190

$$k = \frac{P}{C} = \frac{P}{mC_p} \quad (2)$$

191

192 where P is the instrumental constant of the apparatus, C the heat capacity of the heated
193 material, m the heated mass and C_p the specific heat. The apparatus constant was
194 obtained following Cara et al. (2000b) by fitting of cooling data obtained with a known
195 amount of a reference water suspension of TiO_2 . Experimental thermal parameters of
196 the studied samples were then obtained by using equation 1 and 2.

197

198 **2.3.6. In vitro release of cations**

199 *In vitro* release experiments were performed on 5 mg of therapeutic muds by means of
200 Franz diffusion cells (FDC40020FF, Crown Bio Scientific Inc., Clinton, Permeagear,
201 USA) (contact area 0.64 cm²). The donor and receptor chambers were separated by a
202 dialysis membrane (cut-off 12–14 kDa). Before its use, the membrane was boiled in
203 distilled water for 10 min. Purified water, thermostated at 32 °C, degassed and filtered,
204 was used as receptor phase. At the end of the experiments (20 minutes; minimum
205 typical time of application of mud-packs), the receptor phase was withdrawn, and
206 amount of cations released was dosed by ICP-OES (Optima 8300 ICP-OES
207 Spectrometer, Perkin Elmer, USA).

208

209 **2.4. Statistical analysis**

210 One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with post hoc Sheffé test for multiple
211 comparisons was performed using the software Siphar 4.0 (France). Differences
212 between groups were considered to be significant at a level of P less than 0.05.

213

214 **3. Results and Discussion**

215

216 **3.1. Mineralogy**

217 Mineralogical compositions of the therapeutic muds at different maturation times were
218 obtained on the basis of XRD patterns (Figs. 1 and 2) and chemical compositions (Table
219 1) and compared to those of the initial raw clay materials. XRD patterns of the bulk
220 samples seem to evidence some alteration in the d001 reflection of smectite (Figs. 1A
221 and 2A). In sample I, reflection corresponding to the basal spacing of the Na⁺ smectite
222 was altered to broader diffraction reflections in the matured muds. Nevertheless, XRD
223 patterns of the oriented aggregates clearly show that there were no significant changes
224 as a result of maturation (Figs. 1B and 2B). The observed modifications in the bulk
225 XRD patterns were ascribed to a progressive diminution in the crystallite sizes or in the
226 diffraction domain of the smectites. Similar behavior was also observed by Sánchez et
227 al. (2002). In sample II, during the first 48 h of maturation, the Ca⁺² ions in the smectite
228 interlayer were exchanged by Na⁺ ions coming from the halite dissolution, resulting in a
229 decrease of the interlayer space from $\cong 13.5 \text{ \AA}$ ($\cong 6.0$ 2-theta) (II) to $\cong 12 \text{ \AA}$ ($\cong 7.5$ 2-
230 theta) (II0) (Fig. 2). During the rest of the maturation process, a similar progressive
231 diminution to that previously described for sample I was observed. As regard the
232 mineral impurities, the low amount of dolomite detected in sample I seems to disappear
233 after 48 h of maturation. Similarly, the amount of gypsum in sample II greatly decreases
234 during the first hours of maturation and halite completely dissolved in the first
235 maturation month.

236

237 **3.2. Water content, pH and particle size distribution**

238 Water content of the samples did not significantly change during maturation (Table 2).
239 Potential changes in solid/liquid percentages associated to monthly agitation were
240 therefore neglected.

241 pH of the samples was in the region of the isoelectric point of smectite edges (Avena
242 and de Pauli, 1998), ranging from 7.27 to 8.09 (Table 2). These values were similar to
243 those recently measured in analogous systems and related to the formation of three-
244 dimensional band-type networks (Aguzzi et al., 2013). It is noteworthy that the pH of the
245 samples changed slightly but significantly ($P < 0.001$) as a result of maturation. In both
246 therapeutic muds the pH down slightly and then ascended up to the initial values,
247 suggesting changes in the balance between acid and base cations adsorbed by the solid
248 phase of the muds. Initial decrease in pH during the first maturation month indicated
249 partial dissolution of montmorillonite structure and consequent release of Al³⁺ into the

250 solution as described by several authors (Wieland and Stumm, 1992; Furrer et al., 1993;
251 Bickmore et al., 2001; Sondi et al., 2008). Slow pH increase during the rest of
252 maturation is coherent with the re-adsorption of Al^{3+} cations on the new mixed layer
253 illite-smectite structures forming in the second and third months of maturation
254 (Decarreau, 1985; Golubev et al., 2006).

255 As regard of the aggregation states of the particles during maturation, neither d_{90} , nor
256 d_{50} showed significant changes compared to the initial values, whereas d_{10} increased
257 only after two (sample I, $P < 0.01$) or three months (sample II, $P < 0.05$) of maturation
258 (Table 3). These results are in agreement with those observed in very concentrated clay
259 suspensions in which long maturation time reduced the percentage of individual clay
260 particles (Aguzzi et al., 2013). As a result of the mineralogical changes in crystallite
261 sizes, the amplitude in particle size distribution decreased during maturation, as
262 confirmed by the reduction in SPAN factor values (Table 3).

263

264 **3.3. Rheological properties**

265 As concentrated suspensions of flocculated clay particles, all the therapeutic muds
266 showed typical non-Newtonian viscoplastic flow curves, whatever the maturation time
267 (Fig. 3). The profile of the curves increased with maturation, especially after two
268 months. At the beginning of maturation, the curves showed hysteresis area (especially
269 in the case of sample II) in agreement with the smectite content. The thixotropy of the
270 systems greatly decreased with maturation, corresponding with the alteration of
271 smectites discussed previously.

272 From the flow curves, it was possible to obtain the apparent viscosities (at 200 s^{-1}) and
273 yield point values (calculated according to the Bingham model as the intercept of the
274 linear portion of the flow curve with the stress axis) (Table 4). Both apparent viscosities
275 and yield point values increased significantly ($P < 0.001$) with maturation times. These
276 results are consistent with those observed in concentrated laminar clay gels by Aguzzi et
277 al. (2013). Calcium ions, presented in the liquid phase, promoted face(-)/face(-)
278 contacts and stabilized band-like structures (Lagaly, 2006).

279

280 **3.4. Thermal studies**

281 Experimental specific heats of the therapeutic muds are shown in Table 5. In the table
282 the time required to achieve $32^{\circ}C$ (t_{32}) and the mud temperature after 20 minutes
283 (T_{20min}) (minimum typical time of application of mud-packs), calculated by linear

284 regression of equation 1 ($R^2 > 0.9999$ in all cases), are also included. The experimental
285 values of specific heats were similar to those measured in analogous systems by other
286 authors (Cara et al., 2000b; Legido et al., 2007; Casas et al., 2011, 2013; Caridad et al.,
287 2014; Khiari et al., 2014). In all samples, t_{32} was around 30 min and $T_{20\text{min}}$ was 35°C
288 approximately. These values were able to assure heat transfer between the samples and
289 the skin in normal application procedures. No influence of the composition, neither of
290 the maturation time was observed in the studied thermal parameters ($P > 0.05$). This is
291 congruent with the hypothesis that thermal behaviour of clay muds is mainly dependent
292 of their water content (Cara et al., 2000b).

293

294 **3.5. Cation exchange capacity and in vitro cation release**

295 The total CEC of the therapeutic muds was independent of maturation time (Table 6).
296 However, some significant changes occurred in the exchanged amounts of certain
297 cations (Table 6). Exchangeable Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} decreased in sample I ($P < 0.05$) as a
298 result of dissolution of dolomite and Na^+ values change only after the third month. In
299 sample II, Na^+ values are the only ones changing with time. The amount of
300 exchangeable Na^+ increased during the first maturation month ($P < 0.01$), in agreement
301 with the mineralogical changes previously described (halite dissolution and
302 simultaneous exchange of the Ca^{2+} with Na^+ in the smectite interlayer).

303 The amount of cations released in the Franz cell experiments is reported in Table 7. In
304 all cases, the amount of cations released was lower than the CEC. However, in both
305 samples, the release increased significantly achieved three months of maturation.
306 Release of K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} increased progressively, whereas the release of Na^+
307 showed a sharp increase starting from the second month of maturation. Apparently, the
308 alteration of the smectites by diminution in crystallite sizes improved the release of Na^+
309 cations presented in the smectite interlayer. To explain the reasons of the observed
310 differences in the behavior of the studied cations it would be necessary to perform
311 complementary studies focusing on the possible influence of other metallic cations
312 presented in the systems.

313

314 **4. Conclusions**

315 Maturation of the studied clay samples in the mineral medicinal water of Graena did not
316 induce important mineral alterations except the expected disappearance of soluble
317 minerals. Maturation resulted in a decrease in amplitude of particle size distribution as

318 well as changes in pH of the muds and disappearance of thixotropic behavior of initial
319 smectite gels. Nevertheless, the viscosity and yield point values of the muds increased
320 and the thermal properties remained unaltered. Maturation hardly changed the CEC of
321 the muds, but the amount of cations released, in particular of Na^+ , greatly increased
322 during maturation. According to our results, in the studied systems, maturation makes
323 sense as an operation that increases the release of cations from the therapeutic muds but
324 does not improve their thermal properties. Consequently, in the studied cases, the
325 therapeutic effects associated with thermophysical mechanisms do not require mud
326 maturation. Maturation was only relevant in order to explain the possible chemical
327 effects associated with the use of the therapeutic muds. According to our results, the
328 mud will be mature at two months (maximum of cation release), being necessary to
329 examine the clinical differences associated with that maturation period.

330

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334

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464 solutions at 25°C. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 56, 3339-3355.

465

466 Table 1. Major-element content (w/w %) of the studied samples.

	I ^a	I ₀	I ₁	I ₂	I ₃	II ^a	II ₀	II ₁	II ₂	II ₃
SiO ₂	48.64	48.46	47.65	47.86	48.16	45.83	47.45	48.84	48.78	49.80
Al ₂ O ₃	17.23	17.74	17.55	17.56	17.42	17.23	18.94	19.66	19.75	19.93
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.52	5.98	6.26	6.11	6.32	6.67	8.11	7.97	7.76	8.10
MnO	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.19	0.20	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
MgO	2.35	2.10	2.27	2.28	2.29	2.03	1.68	1.74	1.73	1.72
CaO	7.97	7.27	7.82	7.71	8.01	6.32	1.66	1.63	1.55	1.71
Na ₂ O	1.26	0.97	1.32	1.32	1.29	3.14	2.48	1.91	2.02	2.06
K ₂ O	2.46	2.11	2.41	2.37	2.41	1.72	1.85	1.84	1.83	1.85
TiO ₂	0.76	0.69	0.73	0.72	0.74	0.96	1.00	1.00	0.97	1.04
P ₂ O ₅	0.15	0.11	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.29	0.22	0.23	0.22	0.23
SO ₃	0.57	0.76	0.77	0.74	0.84	5.77	1.72	1.72	1.62	1.73
Cl	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	1.65	1.20	0.71	0.75	0.82
LOI	10.90	13.20	12.70	12.80	12.00	8.56	13.80	12.70	13.10	11.10

467 LOI (loss on ignition)

468 ^aTaken from Sánchez-Espejo et al., 2014.

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471 Table 2. Water content (w/w %) and pH (25 °C) of the samples (mean values ± s.d.; n = 3).

	Water content (w/w %)	pH (25 °C)
I ₀	67.95 ± 1.813	8.04 ± 0.047
I ₁	65.65 ± 0.191	7.83 ± 0.039
I ₂	65.55 ± 0.233	7.92 ± 0.019
I ₃	65.36 ± 0.536	8.09 ± 0.036
II ₀	64.31 ± 0.108	7.45 ± 0.020
II ₁	66.45 ± 0.306	7.27 ± 0.008
II ₂	66.11 ± 0.786	7.37 ± 0.024
II ₃	66.45 ± 0.306	7.43 ± 0.014

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474 Table 3. Statistical diameters and SPAN factor of the samples (mean values ± s.d.; n=3).

	d ₁₀ (µm)	d ₅₀ (µm)	d ₉₀ (µm)	SPAN factor
I ₀	1.32 ± 0.017	4.71 ± 0.093	18.45 ± 0.532	3.63
I ₁	1.31 ± 0.029	4.66 ± 0.098	16.84 ± 1.499	3.34
I ₂	1.33 ± 0.019	4.41 ± 0.092	15.89 ± 0.422	3.31
I ₃	1.40 ± 0.021	4.65 ± 0.081	16.63 ± 1.170	3.27
II ₀	1.24 ± 0.122	3.66 ± 0.198	9.16 ± 0.609	2.16
II ₁	1.25 ± 0.044	3.52 ± 0.158	8.53 ± 0.384	2.07
II ₂	1.31 ± 0.051	3.76 ± 0.215	8.82 ± 0.744	2.00
II ₃	1.39 ± 0.083	3.84 ± 0.288	8.73 ± 0.561	2.01

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477 Table 4. Apparent viscosities (200 s⁻¹, 25°C) and yield values of the samples (mean values ± s.d.; n=6).

	Viscosity (Pa.s)	Yield value (Pa)
I ₀	0.29 ± 0.005	53.89 ± 0.586
I ₁	0.38 ± 0.006	71.88 ± 1.665
I ₂	0.42 ± 0.006	82.10 ± 0.382
I ₃	0.57 ± 0.017	108.89 ± 0.311
II ₀	0.55 ± 0.013	96.19 ± 0.598
II ₁	0.73 ± 0.027	137.1 ± 1.435

II ₂	0.78 ± 0.021	143.61 ± 0.905
II ₃	0.96 ± 0.012	181.05 ± 1.075

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480 Table 5. Thermal parameters of the studied samples (mean values ± s.d.; n=3).

	C _p (J/g K)	t _{32°C} (min)	T _{20 min} (°C)
I ₀	3.21 ± 0.051	30.95 ± 0.056	35.9 ± 0.025
I ₁	3.07 ± 0.139	29.16 ± 0.130	35.4 ± 0.038
I ₂	3.09 ± 0.307	29.46 ± 0.157	35.5 ± 0.042
I ₃	3.08 ± 0.059	29.61 ± 1.333	35.4 ± 0.198
II ₀	2.98 ± 0.004	29.53 ± 0.178	35.5 ± 0.051
II ₁	3.24 ± 0.233	30.14 ± 0.024	35.7 ± 0.003
II ₂	3.15 ± 0.089	28.45 ± 1.561	35.2 ± 0.490
II ₃	3.32 ± 0.397	30.80 ± 0.221	35.9 ± 0.040

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483 Table 6. Cation exchange capacity and amounts of individual cations (meq/100g) (mean values ± s.d.;
484 n=3).

	I ₀	I ₁	I ₂	I ₃
Na	22.11 ± 0.100	21.31 ± 2.038	20.46 ± 0.631	19.65 ± 0.038
K	1.96 ± 0.160	2.06 ± 0.186	1.92 ± 0.107	1.97 ± 0.005
Mg	3.12 ± 0.017	2.98 ± 0.249	2.89 ± 0.095	2.71 ± 0.004
Ca	8.62 ± 0.068	7.81 ± 0.694	7.29 ± 0.333	7.42 ± 0.228
CEC	35.80 ± 0.345	34.16 ± 3.167	32.56 ± 1.165	31.74 ± 0.257

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	II ₀	II ₁	II ₂	II ₃
Na	44.45 ± 0.503	48.05 ± 0.355	48.21 ± 0.315	48.14 ± 0.178
K	4.04 ± 0.255	4.35 ± 0.466	4.58 ± 0.381	4.22 ± 0.728
Mg	8.46 ± 0.305	9.19 ± 0.691	9.09 ± 0.573	8.13 ± 1.152
Ca	22.23 ± 1.147	23.39 ± 1.941	23.48 ± 1.808	22.79 ± 3.749
CEC	79.17 ± 2.211	84.99 ± 3.453	85.37 ± 3.078	83.28 ± 5.808

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487 Table 7. Amount of cations released (meq/100g) from the therapeutic muds (mean values ± s.d.; n = 3).

	I ₀	I ₁	I ₂	I ₃
Na	0.00 ± 0.000	0.10 ± 0.111	12.76 ± 1.577	8.10 ± 1.058
K	0.59 ± 0.102	0.75 ± 0.254	1.47 ± 0.518	1.88 ± 0.294
Mg	0.53 ± 0.140	1.02 ± 0.007	0.72 ± 0.175	0.90 ± 0.080
Ca	1.11 ± 0.330	2.35 ± 0.083	2.21 ± 0.422	2.34 ± 0.102

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	II ₀	II ₁	II ₂	II ₃
Na	0.06 ± 0.007	0.10 ± 0.008	21.62 ± 0.730	14.26 ± 4.603
K	1.14 ± 0.080	1.13 ± 0.066	1.87 ± 0.078	2.35 ± 1.027
Mg	1.94 ± 0.129	2.37 ± 0.242	2.95 ± 0.170	2.82 ± 0.990
Ca	3.93 ± 0.211	4.67 ± 0.398	6.07 ± 0.605	5.97 ± 1.573

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Figure 1. XRD patterns of clay I and its corresponding muds.

Figure 2. XRD patterns of clay II and its corresponding muds.

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Figure 3. Flow curves of the studied samples. Up (muds prepared with clay I) and down (muds prepared with clay II).